

ISSUES OF IMPROVING THE CARTOGRAPHIC SYMBOL SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This thesis discusses the theoretical foundations of the cartographic symbol system, their role in clearly and clearly reflecting the content of the map, and the issues of improving the symbol system in the conditions of modern cartography. Against the background of the development of digital and interactive maps, the standardization of cartographic symbols and increasing their visual effectiveness are of great importance.

The cartographic symbol system is the main communicative tool of the map, providing a concise, clear and understandable representation of geographical objects and phenomena. The shape, color, size and location of the symbols are important factors determining the readability and informativeness of the map. Currently, the rapid development of digital cartography and GIS technologies is placing new demands on the cartographic symbol system. Traditional static symbols are being replaced by flexible, interactive and multi-level symbols. Therefore, improving the symbol system, adapting it to international standards and focusing on user needs has become an urgent issue. Studies show that color contrast and simplicity of symbols directly affect the quick and accurate perception of map information. From this point of view, improving the symbol system based on the principles of cartographic design increases the practical value of maps.

Conclusion

Improving the cartographic symbol system serves to increase the informativeness, accuracy and visual quality of maps. In the conditions of modern cartography, the development of the symbol system is an important factor ensuring the effectiveness of digital maps.